

ISic1323

I.Sicily inscription 1323

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Vicinity of the Odeon

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 22

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Εὐσεβέων κλυτὸν
2. ἄστυ πανόλβιον
3. ἄνδρα ἀνέθηκε ·
4. Ζωσυμιανείδην
5. ἀγνοθετῆρα
6. Σεβῆρον
7. ὄφρα καὶ ἔσομένοισι
8. []OCNZEI βρο
9. [τοῖσιν]

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

The renowned city of pious men erected this statue to Zosimianeides Seberos, agonothete...

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492929

EDCS 39101694

PHI 140817

PHI 316200

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1323. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4353453>